

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY OF 1-4 GRADE STUDENTS BASED ON THE INNOVATION CLUSTER APPROACH

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ANNOTATION

In this article, the issue of developing the creativity of 1-4 grader students based on the innovative cluster approach in today's educational system is described.

Key words: cluster, cluster approach, axiological, psychological, methods, goal, society, initiator, creator, actual.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada bugungi ta'lim tizimida innovatsion klaster yondashuvi asosida 1-4 sinf o'quvchilarining ijodkorligini rivojlantirish masalasi yoritilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: klaster, klaster yondashuvi, aksiologik, psixologik, metodlar, maqsad, jamiyat, tashabbuskor, yaratuvchi, aktual.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается вопрос развития творческих способностей учащихся 1-4 классов на основе инновационного кластерного подхода в современной системе образования.

Ключевые слова: кластер, кластерный подход, аксиологический, психологический, методы, цель, общество, инициатор, творец, актуальный.

INTRODUCTION

In the republic, there is a great demand for people who are enterprising, creative, ready to find new approaches to solving current socio-economic and cultural problems, for those who can live in a new democratic society and be useful for this society. Because every country first of all sees, in the image of its children and the growing young generation, a great power that manifests the characteristics and qualities of this nation and fulfills its eternal dreams. The issue of bringing up a mentally and physically mature generation is a national, state-wide task for us, and the consistent and persistent continuation of our work towards this noble goal is the focus of today's policy. In this regard, the problem of developing the creative activity of an individual is of special relevance today. Creative people always determine the development of civilization, create material and spiritual values distinguished by novelty and abnormality, and help people to see extraordinary things in seemingly ordinary phenomena. [5]

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

4 types of creativity are distinguished in psychological and pedagogical studies:

- simple (appears at preschool and primary school period). Stereotypes that must be overcome in schoolchildren during this period;
- stimulating - effective (activity is determined under the influence of an external stimulus);
- heuristic (the activity is creative by nature, the search for new, original or more rational ways of solving problems is carried out);

- real (independently found regularity acts as a new problem):

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Adhering to the position of scientists who define creative abilities as an independent factor as developmental factors that are the result of teaching the creative activities of schoolchildren, we distinguish the following components of creative abilities of young students:

- creative thinking;
- creative imagination;
- applying methods of organizing creative activity. [3]

To develop students' creative thinking and imagination, it is necessary to develop the following skills:

- classification of objects, situations, events on different bases;
- establishing causal relationships;
- see relationships between systems and identify new connections;
- review during system development;
- make assumptions about the future;
- distinguishing opposite signs of the object;
- identifying and forming contradictions;
- distinguishing conflicting features of parties in space and time;
- reflection of spatial objects;
- use of different orientation systems in imaginary space;
- object representation based on selected properties.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

We think that it is appropriate to use the innovative cluster approach to solve the above issues. Here, let's explain the concept of cluster and its essence. A cluster is referred to a certain system, but this system is unique, in which the elements added to it improve the work of this system, but the removal of any element from it does not lead to the breakdown of this system. Cluster systems are characterized by effectiveness, stability, and can be easily upgraded, updated and enhanced in a variety of ways. The advantage of the cluster is its global scale, openness, flexibility and simplicity of management.

The need to address to the cluster approach lies in the fact that the cluster has priority as a form of organization with the feature of increasing the effectiveness of the technological education system and uniting the actions of interested parties. One of the main conditions of clusters is their territorial strategy, because educational clusters develop without separating from their territory.

Therefore, a cluster is the role of participating subjects who united for a common goal in certain contractual relations and management of the activities of those subjects. [1]

The topic "Methods of using natural and various materials in application works" is relevant in improving the creativity of the 4th grade students at general secondary schools in the sense that it is necessary to properly organize the teaching of technology and attracting students to work are the most urgent tasks of today.

The educational value of elementary school Technology lessons consists of edifying students to manual labor, bringing them up to be creative and mature people, edifying them to self-service, improving labor skills, and in the process of practical training it consists of forming skills and skills, directing them to the profession, educating students from an aesthetic point of view through application work, and creating a foundation for students to become

professional. Also, in the process of creating various compositions from paper, natural and various materials in the direction of application, the 4th grade students develop their creative abilities.

In technology lessons, the main problems are studied through the cluster approach. In the 4th grade technology lessons, students use various methods to increase their creativity through application work, study the state of their problems in determining their goals and tasks, and develop the following recommendations.

- studying the problems of levelling up the creativity of elementary school students through application work and defining goals and objectives;
- analysis of information relative to the topic to levelling up the creativity of elementary school students through application works;
- to study successful work methods in increasing the creativity of primary school students through application works;
- increasing the effectiveness of creative education of elementary school students;
- conducting continuous research on the use of various methods to level up the creativity of primary school students through application work.
- development of conditions for ensuring the individual approach of the teacher in levelling up the creativity of elementary school students through application works. [3]

In order to ensure that students of 1-4th grade can effectively use the opportunities available in technology classes to inspire their creativity, and acquire knowledge, skills and qualifications through application work, additional practical training and activities of clubs will be organized. It is possible to achieve effective results in the implementation of ri.

In the process of solving the problem, the advantages and perspectives of educating 4th grade students in stimulating their creativity through application work were revealed; specific scientific pedagogical-psychological and methodical aspects of using different methods to increase students' creativity through application works were highlighted; methods and tools were used in experimental works and effective results were achieved.

Ways of using application works to increase the creativity of 1st-4th grade students, their age characteristics, personal, psychological and physiological qualities were taken into account in the process of various technological education. Students' knowledge and learning skills were monitored in various ways according to the state educational standards, and during the practical training organized on the use of application works to increase the creativity of the 4th grade students, the intended goal and result were achieved. [4]

CONCLUSION:

It can be concluded that, the clustering aof the educational space makes it possible to modernize education and build an educational system based on a comprehensive model. It includes components such as goals, methods, forms, tools, mechanisms of students' acquisition of values, and control elements in the educational system. Therefore, the use of an innovative pedagogical cluster in technological education is the integration of educational programs and production needs.

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